

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B308
Date: 18 July 2007
Take Off 11:47:29
Landing: 15:43:36
Flight Time 3h56m07

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Al Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Mission Scientist 2	John Marsham	Leeds University
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	VACC 1	Angela Dean	Leeds
10	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
11	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Nephelometers	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
14			
15			
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Flight Track:

B308 Track 18-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B308
 Date: 18th July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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111914		event	0.22 kft	156	INU to Nav
112445		event	0.22 kft	156	GIN start
113746		Start-Up	0.23 kft	156	
114231		event	0.23 kft	167	taxy
114321		Video	0.23 kft	329	start FFC & RFC
114729		T/O	0.22 kft	212	Baden Baden
115033		event	5.6 kft	176	JW/Nevzorov zero
115741	120120	Profile 1	6.0 - 2.4 kft	278	
120120	121400	Run 1.1	2.4 - 2.3 kft	208	
120715		event	2.3 kft	203	Heimann cal
121333		event	2.3 kft	202	JW/Nevzorov zero
121520	121945	Profile 2	2.3 - 7.0 kft	093	
122030	123253	Run 2.1	7.1 - 7.0 kft	014	
123412	123807	Profile 3	7.0 - 3.4 kft	260	
124053	124209	Profile 3	3.4 - 2.4 kft	206	
124210	125145	Run 3.1	2.4 kft	202	
124306		event	2.4 kft	203	JW/Nevzorov zero
125244	125643	Profile 4	2.4 - 7.0 kft	092	
125745	131031	Run 4.1	7.0 kft	011	
125923		event	7.0 kft	009	JW/Nevzorov zero
131159	131405	Profile 5	7.0 - 9.0 kft	219	
131333		event	8.6 kft	184	JW/Nevzorov zero
131451	131544	Profile 5	9.0 - 10.0 kft	181	
131605	131852	Profile 5	10.0 - 13.0 kft	200	
131733		Video	11.6 kft	200	FFC RFC tape 2
132043	132309	Profile 5	13.0 - 15.0 kft	011	
132454		event	14.7 kft	033	JW/Nevzorov zero
132629	132918	Run 5.1	13.0 kft	112	
132734		event	13.0 kft	136	JW/Nevzorov zero
133925		event	13.0 kft	193	JW/Nevzorov zero
134101	134243	Run 5.2	13.1 - 13.0 kft	033	
134438	134538	Run 5.3	13.0 kft	178	
134825	134928	Run 5.4	13.0 kft	020	
135041	135313	Run 5.5	13.0 kft	219	
135634	135844	Run 5.6	13.0 kft	036	
140436	140645	Run 5.7	13.0 kft	021	
141238	141444	Run 5.8	13.0 kft	033	
142052		event	14.5 kft	006	JW/Nevzorov zero
142635	142717	Run 5.9	13.1 - 13.0 kft	203	
143004	143235	Run 5.10	13.0 kft	006	
143536	143805	Run 5.11	13.0 kft	216	
143950	144239	Run 5.12	13.0 kft	040	
150123	150453	Profile 6	13.0 - 17.0 kft	195	
150654	150959	Profile 7	17.0 - 14.1 kft	358	
151134	151547	Profile 7	14.0 - 10.1 kft	189	
151738	152052	Run 6.1	10.0 kft	004	
152230	152825	Run 6.2	10.0 kft	200	
153103	153453	Profile 8	10.0 - 5.4 kft	329	
153548	153845	Run 7.1	5.4 kft	297	
154336		Land	0.26 kft	214	Baden baden
154925		Shutdown	0.27 kft	146	48 46.91N 08 05.35E

B308 Track 18-JUL-07

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goal of UK-COPS is to determine the properties of the aerosols that will likely be ingested into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds . We wish to examine:

- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will either be 2 flights per day: one in clear air to measure the properties of the aerosols and one later in the convective clouds; or the two parts will be flown in a single flight. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. There may be coordination with the DO-128 in Boxes A and B. The French and German Falcons may also be operating in the area.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe and calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS -
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode
- VACC - in straight and level clear-air, 10 min runs; during cloud work and profiles, single temperature.

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B308
Date: 18 July 2007
Mission Scientists: Phil Brown
TO Time: 12:50 local
In the box: 14:00 local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air in Rhine Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels.
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A. stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B. several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area.
3. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
4. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).
2 x Rhine Valley aerosol legs (70 mins)
2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible. Relay cloud top info to the DO-128.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

- A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.
- A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.
- A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.
- A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.4 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

- B.1 Proceed to 0°C
- B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.
- B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.
- B.5 Repeat for -10°C, -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min)

B308

18/07/2007

Mission Scientist Debrief:

Phil Brown

1. Assessment of flight

Climbout to 6000ft as usual in preparation for low level runs. Descent to 2500ft on QNH, which is a couple of hundred feet or so below the cloudbase. Commence run 1.1. Cumulus tops visible over the Vosges region are deepening but not yet to the freezing level. Considerable structure seen in aerosol and tracer variables, apparently connected to convective transport in the sub-cloud layer.

Profile climb to 7000ft over the Black Forest. This is higher than normal due to low cloudbase inhibiting VFR flight legs over the mountains. Nevertheless this leg could provide useful information on tracers and aerosols in clear air within the cloud layer, after detrainment from the clouds.

Descent initially to 3500ft due to delays with conflicting traffic. Final descent to 2500ft meant next southbound leg (3.1) started a little way along the valley. Similar sorts of structure in aerosols to what was seen on previous low level leg.

Climb to 7000ft for final aerosol leg. S.end of this track is still affected by As/Ac from the frontal zone, possibly inhibiting cumulus build up. At n.end of leg, cloud tops are building above flight level.

Climb to FL130, with multiple layers of broken As from FL116 above. FL130 appears still to be within the moist layer. Aim for an ascending cumulus top in NE corner of box A/B but had to turn within cloud in order to avoid infringing boundary. Seven further legs at this level sampling cloud tops just reaching to this level or up to 1000ft above. Some of these have decent updrafts of a few m/s. Then ascend to FL145 attempting to track cloud top upwards but by this time it has drifted out of the area ☹️ Cloud tops often have extensive pileus caps around as they ascend into the moist layer. General cloud structure seems to be of cumulus turrets rising into a mass that extends downshear from the initial ascent.

Four further legs at FL130 attempting to sample clouds more in centre of the box, but it is becoming apparent that convective activity is now weakening. Profile ascent FL130 to 170 then descent to FL100, with a view to further legs sampling within the cloud layer. However, only one cloud penetration achieved as the southern part of the box is becoming largely cloud free.

Profile descent to 5500ft (cloudbase at 6000), for low level leg over M and H supersites. This started just to South of M, but was reasonably overhead H. Unable to reach R as required to avoid traffic in the Rhine valley and descend rapidly to land.

2. Summary of weather conditions

Old frontal zone lying roughly SW to NE across COPS region and dissipating. As the cloud breaks, daytime heating gives convective development, base initially ~2800ft in the valley and maybe 5-6000ft over the BF.

Convection eventually grew to maximum of about 15000ft but only when it drifted out of the NE corner of the COPS box.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...308 Date 18/7/07 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Camera timechecked vs Horace.
1140					Cu, 1/8 to S, 2/8 to N in frontal zone has dissipated as forecast. Cu over BFF showing signs of vertical development
1147					t/o FK13
					cloudbase close to 2500 but scattered
1150					Cu over the mtns seem more rooted in the valley boundary layers. Some tops reaching to about 6000ft.
120120		2500			Start R1.1 just below base.
					Some Cu tops over Vosges getting deep. but not yet to freezing level?
1207		"			Variable Cnc 3000-10000.
121400		"			End R1.1
					Profile 2 T/Td repeats quite well the previous.
122030		7000ft			R2.1 Cu tops just below.
					Cu layers below 4500ft. T = +10
		"			Estimate tops over Vosges not much above.
122335		"			3/8 As still roughly aligned SW/NE in the frontal zone. Estimate at 9-10000ft.
122825		"			Tops to ~ 7500 in this area. ~ 3 mi left of track avoiding cl.
123253		"			End 2.1, T slightly lower at N end.
124210		2500			Start 3.1 a bit way along descent delay.
1247		"			Vosges tops still look below freezing level
125037		"			Cnc variable but background rising along road.
125145		"			End 3.1
125620					Cu base ~ 6000ft over BFF during profile

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...308 Date 18/7/07 Name Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
125745	4.1	7000			Start. Still As/Ac above. Seems to be some Cu tops reaching into it at W end of run.
/		7000			wind 4ms ⁻¹ / 260 deg
130531		"			seems like slightly deeper build up here, some Cu tops dissipating at this level.
131031	4.1	"		48 48 N 8 24 E	End.
131159					Profile 5 definite Cu punching into stable layer. Pileus.
/		11600			just into thin As. -0.2
/		13000			still in As - 2 layers. -2.3
/		13000			cloud tops 1000 above.
/					had to turn in cloud as right on edge of box
134101	5.2	13000			not poss. to reach the cloud! -2.7.
	5.3	"			cell just growing to this level. 1.2 gm ⁻³
	5.4				cloud not growing. just mixed
	5.5				just clipped the pileus topped cell. 0.5 gm ⁻³ mostly downdraft?
135634	5.6	"			pileus on approach side. no radar echo.
/					can see cells growing up along wind / shear.
	5.7				Pileus initially.
1412	5.8				now grown ~ 1000 above. no precip updraft now. no radar.
	6.1	14500			cloud now out of area.
	5.9	13000			V. quick attempt to hit cloud top - just failed, will make another run.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...308 Date 18/7/07 Name Page 3 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	5.10	13000			
143507		"			moving towards cloud more in centre of area.
143536	5.11	"			just over top of cloud.
143950	5.12	"			cloud top now above. -2.5
1445					clouds to SW all lower, seem to be decaying.
1452				Cu	all gone from valley.
1459					Clouds now dissipating. Will profile to 170 then back to 100.
150123	P6	13000			2 clouds off out to S of box that have descended above 170 and glaciated.
	P7	17000			
	end	10000			moist layer of frontal zone still where it was. +3.8
	6.1	10000			
151850					in cloud, brief.
152230	6.2	"			will be clear of cloud. cent tops reaching this level.
	P8	"			for 5500, 2000/min initially.
	↓	6000			cloudbase.
	P8	5500			
15354	R71	"			just to S of M supercite.
					O/h M but miss R
1544					land FK13.
					3h 56.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B308

Date: 18 July 2007	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:58			checked														
12:06				check	check								check				
12:11																Synch sent to ffssp	
12:15																Sid2 restarted sid on flag red, now ok	
12:19																Ffssp restarted	
12:25																Ffssp sync	
12:35																Sid2 restarted b308b	
12:47																Psap flow very noisy centered around 0.6 units	
<p>Many fault indications precluded normal logging:</p> <p>FFSSP Needed several restarts due to wild data values. SYNCH command usually worked. In particular 13:30 cloud penetration, nothing seen on ffssp. The system had hung on 'normal' data readings – not obvious. Synch command sorted this out.</p> <p>PCASP Flow very noisy, not believable. Noise bursts coincided with cloud penetrations.</p> <p>SID1 Appears ok</p> <p>SID2 "STOPPED RESPONDING" flag comes up frequently but data history strip chart seems unaffected. Restarting with new flight number (a,b c...) makes flag reset ok.</p> <p>2DP performance uncertain</p> <p>2DC performance uncertain</p> <p>CIP Appears to be sampling and recording, screen displays do not show data Disc full error, flight files moved to D: folder b308 restarted as b308ext</p>																	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B308 **T/O:** 114729
Date of flight: 18/07/07 **Land:** 154336

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>Y</p> <p>0</p>	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b308_tas</p> <p>Start = 114800 End = 154300</p> <p>Time data processed to = 144324 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 59, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>X = _TAS Y = (X+1) = _tas_2D</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Checked data present in M5</p> <p>Correlated? Not poss just now.</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B308
Date of Flight: 18/07/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 2 Vol flow rate = 1.0 114800 154300
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2dpcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Checked data present Merged OK?

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B308**.....

 Date 18/7/07.....

 Operator's name: Aw.....

 Page 1 of 1.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
110000								PREFLIGHT OK. Both nephs zero'd.
115700	P1 ↓	5500ft	12.3	29.8	36.4	↘	9.6C	start P1 ↓ water to +6c.
120120	P1.1	2500ft	13.5	56	76	↗	6C	start P1.1. RAMPING wet neph RH up. Set water to +40
120450		- "-	11.4	62	81	↗	40	reduce flow & set water to +43
120755	- "-	- "-	14.3 15.9	58.8	83.3	↘	45	ramp down + flow up
121400	- "-	- "-	16	62.8	63.9	↘	23.6	end P1.1
121520	P2	2500ft ↗	15.6	55.3	56.8	↘	19.4	start P2 ascent. Preheater on
121945		FL070	13.8 15.3	36 25.3	36.8	↘	12.9	end P2
122030	P2.1	- "-	14.0	26.2	35.7	↗	12.4	Start Run. RAMPING UP.
122410	"	"	13.7	24.6	57.3	↗	42	mid run.
122500	- "-	- "-	9.7	23.3	71.9	↗	43.6	Set flow lower.
122830	- "-	- "-	16	26.9	82.7	↘	45	↻ ramp down + flow up
123253	P2.1	FL070	16	22.6	44.9	↘	23.8	end run.
123412	P3	FL070 ↓	16.0	22.3	40.1	↘	20.2	Start P3 descent
124210	P3/P3.1	2500ft	11.1	53.6	42.2	↗	9.6	end P3/start P3.1 ramping up / slow down (preheater 'im h7%. 27c temp 3
125145	P3.1	- "-	9.7	54.9	86.4	-	45	end run. interesting humidigram this run XXXX .
125244	P4	2400ft ↗						start P4 to FL070. will ramp down during next run.
125643	P4	FL070	13.5	24.9	86.2	-	45	end P4.
125745	P4.1	- "-	15.1	24.3	85.2	↘	45	start run. ramping down. / flow up
131031	4.1	FL070	15.1	22.6	33.1	↘	12:	end run / end wet neph work - Draining down.

CVI log B308

7/18/07 11:57:43 AM profile descent
7/18/07 12:01:19 PM run 1.1
7/18/07 12:13:59 PM end of run 1.1
7/18/07 12:15:35 PM profile climb
7/18/07 12:20:25 PM start of run 2.1
7/18/07 12:32:50 PM end of run 2.1
7/18/07 12:34:22 PM profile descent
7/18/07 12:42:10 PM strat of run 3.1
7/18/07 12:51:42 PM end of run 3.1
7/18/07 12:52:44 PM profile ascent
7/18/07 12:57:44 PM start of run 4.1
7/18/07 1:10:29 PM end of run 4.1
7/18/07 1:12:09 PM profile climb
7/18/07 1:25:06 PM going to cvi mode
7/18/07 1:26:39 PM start of run 5.1
7/18/07 1:41:02 PM start of run 5.2
7/18/07 1:42:41 PM end of run 5.2
7/18/07 1:44:36 PM start of run 5.3
7/18/07 1:45:37 PM end of run 5.3
7/18/07 1:48:19 PM start of run 5.4
7/18/07 1:49:25 PM end of run 5.4
7/18/07 1:50:30 PM start of run 5.5
7/18/07 1:53:12 PM end of run 5.5
7/18/07 1:56:23 PM start of run 5.6
7/18/07 1:58:45 PM end of run 5.6
7/18/07 2:04:28 PM start of run 5.7
7/18/07 2:06:38 PM end of run 5.7
7/18/07 2:12:27 PM start of run 5.8
7/18/07 2:14:40 PM end of run 5.8
7/18/07 2:15:28 PM profile climb
7/18/07 2:26:02 PM profile descent
7/18/07 2:26:33 PM start of run 6.1
7/18/07 2:27:04 PM start of run 5.9
7/18/07 2:27:13 PM end of run 5.9
7/18/07 2:29:46 PM start of run 5.10
7/18/07 2:32:32 PM end of run 5.10
7/18/07 2:35:29 PM start of run 5.11
7/18/07 2:38:09 PM end of run 5.11
7/18/07 2:39:41 PM start of run 5.12
7/18/07 2:42:34 PM end of run 5.12
7/18/07 3:15:16 PM out of cvi mode
7/18/07 3:17:41 PM start of run 6.1
7/18/07 3:18:24 PM back to cvi mode
7/18/07 3:21:03 PM end of run 6.1
7/18/07 3:22:24 PM start of run 6.2

Flight:

B308

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:27:24

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:51:42

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B308

Date: 18/07/2007

Instruments

Time server failed – HORACE reboot then ok

Aircraft

None

Satcom-H Calls

Dornier crew

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 18/7/07

Flight No: B308

Pre-Flighter: BW

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	FI on inboard
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezovorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	? boxes in drawer
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Paper needed</div>				
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	No zero cal
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	VNC problem (me)
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	Behind CPT seat
Proceed to External Checks				
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B308:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	23 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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